

MULTI-OBJECTIVE MECHANICAL OPTIMISATION OF LATTICE STRUCTURES

Athina Kontopoulou^{1a}, Bing Zhang^{1b}, Fabrizio Scarpa^{1c}, and Giuliano Allegri^{1d}

¹Bristol Composites Institute (BCI), Aerospace Engineering Department, University of Bristol, Queens Building, BS8 1TR, UK.

^aathina.kontopoulou@bristol.ac.uk

^bb.zhang@bristol.ac.uk

^cf.scarpa@bristol.ac.uk

^dgiuliano.allegri@bristol.ac.uk

Keywords: Lattice Materials; Homogenisation; Finite element method; Evolutionary Optimisation.

ABSTRACT

The progress of additive manufacturing technologies has considerably widened the design space of lattice materials, providing the means for tailoring their mechanical performance. This study explores the influence of tapering the struts within lattice-materials periodic unit cells, aiming to maximise the compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses via an evolutionary optimisation algorithm. The modelling framework is based on a volumetric homogenisation technique of the representative unit cell, employing Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs). A lattice topology generated by superimposing the basic lattice unit cells of the Body Centred Cubic (BCC), the Face-Centred cubic (FCC) and the Simple Cubic (SC) was optimised by this modelling approach. Relative density and additive manufacturing constraints have been considered in the optimisation. The optimised lattice configurations with tapered struts show an 11% enhancement of the specific compressive stiffness and a 5% increase for the specific out-of-plane shear stiffness, compared to non-tapered lattice structures with relative density of 0.40.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lattice materials have a cellular periodic architecture, generated by the repetition of 3D networks of truss elements. These materials have been extensively researched in view of their use in aerospace, automotive and biomedical applications, because of their unique combination of highly tailorable specific properties, in particular strength and energy absorption capability.

The huge technological progress in additive manufacturing techniques has broadened the design space of lattice materials, as it enables the creation of lattice materials with a greater degree of complexity, precision, and material diversity, in a time- and cost-effective manner. Several studies have investigated the effect of lattice unit-cell architectures on mechanical properties, especially for the Body-Centred Cubic (BCC) topology. It has been found that increasing the height of the unit cell and, consequently, the angle between BCC struts, results in enhanced compressive stiffness [1]. Osman *et al.* [2] showed that a higher angle in the octet-truss unit cell improved the specific energy absorption, as well as the dimensional accuracy when manufactured by Selective Laser Melting (SLM). This is because when increasing the height of the unit cell and, consequently, the overhang angle between the struts to more than 35°, the lattices become self-supporting, making the manufacturing via conventional 3D printing techniques [3] much easier.

Other studies in the open literature have focussed on varying the radius of the struts along their length, or creating fillets around the nodes, such as in Triply Periodic Minimal Surface (TPMS) lattices. Regarding the latter, Yang *et al.* [4] demonstrated that rounded fillets around the nodes can reduce the local stress concentration at the nodes, and thus improve the fatigue and compressive performance of a BCC structure. Similarly, Xiao *et al.* [5] characterised BCC and Simple-Cubic (SC) lattices defined via implicit surfaces, which have continuously varying curvatures at the nodes. This enhanced the energy absorption capability under compression. Zhao *et al.* [6] conducted a parametric study of tapered, hexagonal-shaped struts in BCC lattice structures. They observed that the deformation behaviour changed from bending- to stretching-dominated, increasing the elastic modulus up to 67%. Tancogne-Dejean *et al.* [7] demonstrated that tapering the radius of the struts in an octet truss lattice can increase the energy-absorbing capacity under static and dynamic compression loads.

This work investigates the design space of lattice materials, aiming to optimise two key mechanical performance metrics, namely the compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses. These are very important when lattice materials are employed as cores in sandwich panels. Here, we aim to provide some useful insights regarding the effect of tailoring geometric features of lattice architectures, with emphasis on tapering the unit cell struts. We consider a “superimposed” lattice topology, entailing the combination of basic unit cells, such as the Body Centred Cubic (BCC), the Face-Centred Cubic (FCC) and Simple Cubic (SC) structures, as shown in Figure 1. The resulting lattice topology is numerically optimised via a genetic algorithm embedded within a unit cell (UC) finite element (FE) simulation framework. The effects of the height of the representative volume element (Y_{RVE}), strut radii (R_b , R_m) and the characteristic ratio (α) defining the length of the uniform cross-section of the struts are explored. These geometric parameters are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Superposition of simple lattice structures: (a) BCC, (b) SC, (c) FCC; (d) the resulting superimposed lattice topology.

Figure 2: (a) Tapered strut representation, with relevant parameters shown; (b) Unit cell with tapered struts.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material properties and the manufacturing constraints considered in the optimisation must account for the specific capabilities of the 3D printing method adopted. Hereby, stereolithography is used (form 3+ 3D printer [8]) because of its high dimensional accuracy and resolution. The material properties employed in the FE modelling framework were obtained by testing 3D printed dog bone coupons made of Formlabs “grey” resin under quasi-static tensile loading. The post-curing methodology for the 3D printed dog-bone coupons is those recommended in the Formlabs “grey” resin datasheet [9]. The post-cure temperature was 60°C, applied for 1 hour. The tests were conducted according to the ASTM standard D638–4. The resulting material properties are listed in Table 1.

Young modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Density (g/cm ³)
2.78	0.277	1.08

Table 1: Material properties of grey resin Formlabs.

3 MICRO-MODELLING FRAMEWORK

3.1 Elastic Homogenisation

Periodic materials and structures can be modelled employing only one Representative Volume Element (RVE), i.e. a unit cell, to reduce significantly the computational cost. To accurately compute the effective elastic properties of the RVE lattices, a FE-based volumetric homogenisation technique was used together with the application of strain-controlled Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs). PBCs impose a periodic uniform strain field to the RVE boundaries ($\partial\Omega_{RVE}$), as required for the computation of the homogenised elastic properties, pairing the mesh nodes of the opposite boundaries through linear constrain equations [10]:

$$u_x^+ - u_x^- = \varepsilon_{ij}^0(x^+ - x^-) \forall x \in \partial\Omega_{RVE} \quad (1)$$

where x^+ , x^- are the coordinates of opposite paired nodes, ε_{ij}^0 is the applied strain and u is the resulting displacement on $\partial\Omega_{RVE}$. In order to populate the material stiffness matrix and calculate the elastic moduli through the homogenisation process for each RVE, six static analyses were performed on each unit cell generated during the optimisation process. Each of these static analyses yields one column of the homogenised stiffness matrix. The analysis cases include three uniaxial tensile load scenarios and three simple shear cases, as discussed in ref. [11]. The expression of the components of the material stiffness matrix is:

$$C_{\alpha\beta} = \bar{\sigma}_\alpha = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \int_{V_{EFF}} \sigma_\alpha \, dV \approx \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \sum_{el=1}^N \sigma_\alpha^{el} V^{el} \text{ when } \bar{\varepsilon}_\beta = 1. \quad (2)$$

3.2 Finite Element Implementation

3D solid FE models of the lattice structure were created using ABAQUS®, via a dedicated pre-processor written in Python. This translates the genomes generated by the genetic algorithm into solid FE models. For the models, solid quadratic tetrahedral (C3D10) elements were utilised, with an element size of 0.25 mm. This element size was determined in a mesh convergence study when observing less than 1% variation of the compressive stiffness with a total number of elements of 26,528, as illustrated in Figure 3. For the lattice configuration from Figure 2(d), i.e. all radii equal to 0.3 mm and an RVE height of 8.0 mm, (see the red point in Figure 3), it yields a compressive stiffness of 150.72 MPa following the convergence study.

Figure 3: Mesh convergence study of the lattice model.

3.3 Analytical Validation

To validate the homogenisation FE modelling framework described above, a BCC lattice structure with a constant RVE length and height of 5 mm was considered. The analytical expression of the BCC homogenised Young's modulus, based on the assumption of Euler-Bernoulli beam behaviour of individual struts is [12]:

$$E_{BCC_{Euler}}^* = \rho_{rel} \frac{E_s}{1 + 2(l/2r)^2} = \sqrt{3} \pi \left(\frac{2r}{l}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_s}{1 + 2(l/2r)^2} \quad (3)$$

where E_s is the stiffness of the “dense” material, r is the radius of the BCC struts, and l is the length of the RVE when considering an isotropic unit cell arrangement with $X_{RVE} = Y_{RVE} = Z_{RVE}$.

If Timoshenko beam theory is used to describe the behaviour of the struts, the homogenised Young's modulus is given by [13]:

$$E_{BCC_{Timoshenko}}^* = \frac{4\sqrt{3}E_s}{\left[\frac{l^2}{\pi r^2} + \frac{l^4}{2\pi r^4} + \frac{1.000352l^2(1 + \nu_s)\sqrt{2}}{r^2} \right]} \quad (4)$$

where ν_s is the Poisson's ratio of the dense material.

In Figure 4, the analytical predictions of the elastic modulus are compared against the FE analysis results. The numerical results are in good agreement with the theoretical predictions for a strut aspect ratio smaller than 0.07. This has been expected, as beam-based analytical models become less accurate as the aspect ratio of the struts is increased, because of the increasing shear compliance and the finite deformability of the nodes at the strut connections.

Figure 4: Comparison of theoretical and numerical results of elastic modulus for a range of strut aspect ratios r/L .

3.4 Optimisation algorithm

For the optimisation of the lattice structure, the MATLAB parallelised implementation of a multi-objective genetic algorithm was employed [14]. A parallel pool of 5 workers was used to reduce the computational time.

The genetic algorithm searches for the minimum solution to the objectives. As here the desired objectives are the maximisation of compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses, the use of minus transforms the minimisation to a maximisation problem. The objectives used are the following:

$$f_1(x) = -\log(E_2) \quad (5)$$

$$f_2(x) = -\log(G_{23}) \quad (6)$$

The lower and upper bounds of the design variables were based on the actual capabilities of the Stereolithography printer. These are summarized in Table 2. The height of the RVE (Y_{RVE}) was varied between 5.0 and 10.0 mm, in order to achieve self-supporting configurations with strut angles (θ) exceeding 45° .

The tapering factor (β) is a ratio between the bottom radius close to the nodes (R_b) and the radius in the middle of the strut (R_m), i.e.:

$$\beta = \frac{R_m}{R_b} \quad (7)$$

The struts radii at the bottom (R_b) and the middle (R_m) were both free to vary from 0.3 to 0.8 mm. Thus, $\beta < 1$ represents thin-waisted struts, while $\beta = 1$ gives a constant radius across the full length of the strut. Finally, $\beta > 1$ corresponds to struts that are swollen in their central region. As illustrated in Figure 2, the ratio α defines the strut region of uniform cross section with radius R_b (recall Figure 2a). In the literature, ref. [15] considers $\alpha = 0.8$, while ref. [7] explores the case $\alpha = 2.0$. To investigate the effect α , we let it vary within the range from 0.1 to 2.0 in the optimisation.

Finally, the values of the relative density ($RD - \bar{\rho}$), i.e. the ratio between the homogenised RVE density ρ^* relative to the solid density ρ_s , for the optimised lattice architectures are considered, namely: 0.30, 0.35 and 0.40. The relative density of the lattice structures can be calculated as the ratio of lattice volume (V_{lat}) to the volume of the RVE (V_{RVE}), i.e.:

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} = \frac{V_{lat}}{V_{RVE}} \quad (8)$$

Design variables	Type	Lower bound	Upper bound
Y_{RVE}	Continuous	5.0 mm	10.0 mm
R_b	Continuous	0.3 mm	0.8 mm
R_m	Continuous	0.3 mm	0.8 mm
α	Continuous	0.1	2.0

Table 2: Lower and upper bounds of all design variables.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The multi-objective optimisation gives a Pareto front, which is a set of all optimal solutions that cannot be improved further without sacrificing at least one of the objectives. The points located close to the central region of the Pareto front represent genomes that equally satisfy both objectives.

A first set of optimisations for different population sizes (5, 10 and 15 chromosomes times the number of three independent variables including: the Y_{RVE} , R_m , R_b) were carried out, fixing the RD at 0.4 and imposing $\alpha = 0.8$. The design variables were free to vary based on the bounds mentioned in section 3.4. In Figure 5, a comparison of the resulting Pareto fronts is presented, suggesting a weak sensitivity of the final optimisation results on the population size. A population size of 15 individuals times the number of independent variables was selected for the other optimisation scenarios that will be discussed in what follows.

Figure 5: Pareto front for relative density constraint 0.4.

A second set of optimisation runs included 3 different RD values, namely 0.30, 0.35 and 0.40, while setting $\alpha = 0.8$. The height of the UC and the radii (R_b , R_m) were allowed to vary based on the aforementioned upper and lower bounds in Table 2.

To explore the effect of the uniform cross-section length parameter (α), the lattice configuration was finally optimised varying α , Y_{RVE} , R_b and R_m , with RD kept constant at 0.35. In Figure 6, the Pareto front resulting from this last set of optimisation runs is compared with those obtained at constant $\alpha = 0.8$. As can be observed this Pareto front is coincident with the one of equal RD.

In Figure 7, we can see that all four optimisations yielded an optimal tapering ratio $\beta \sim 0.7$ compared to the light green scatter points with $\beta = 1$, which represent the non-tapered UC. Specifically, the average optimum tapering factor β was found to be equal to 0.85 for RD = 0.30 and 0.7 for RD = 0.35 and 0.40.

It is also noteworthy that such an optimal β value is independent of the objectives, as can be observed in Figure 7 between (a) and (b).

Figure 6: Pareto fronts for RD 0.40, 0.35, 0.30 and the factor α with RD 0.35.

Figure 7: (a) Specific compressive stiffness as a function of β , and (b) specific out-of-plane shear stiffness as a function of β for relative densities $RD = 0.40, 0.35$ and 0.30 and varying the factor α .

In Figure 8, it is shown that the optimum height of the unit cell seems ranged between 6 mm to 7 mm for the maximum specific out-of-plane shear stiffness. However, it approached the upper bound of 10 mm for maximum specific compressive stiffness, independently from the imposed relative density values. Only the height of the RVE appears to vary according to the objectives. Hence it is observed that the β value has a relatively weak influence on the height of the unit cell or how well a specific objective (i.e. either maximum compressive stiffness or homogenised out-of-plane modulus) is satisfied.

To quantify the effect of tapered struts, we compare the specific compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses of uniform cross-section configurations with equal relative densities at different Y_{RVE} values. In Figure 7 and Figure 8, the light green points show the performance of configurations with a uniform cross-section ($\beta = 1$), compared to results with equal RD and Y_{RVE} . The highest increase of the objectives is observed mainly at lower Y_{RVE} values between 6 and 8 mm, at each RD we explored. More in detail, the results show that for balanced optimum mechanical performance, intermediate values of height and

tapering should be selected. Because of the tapering, an 11% enhancement of the specific compressive stiffness is observed; for the out-of-plane shear stiffness, a 5-6% improvement is obtained. For instance, in a UC with $Y_{RVE} = 6.9$ mm and $RD = 0.30$, a tapering value $\beta = 0.85$ would increase the specific compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses by 11.34% and 6.56% respectively.

As shown in Figure 9, the uniform cross-section length parameter α is optimised between the values of 0.55 and 1.1 for both objectives, compared to the 0.8 (light green points) considered in the previous optimisations. The optimum α is averaged as 0.82 ± 0.14 , a value close to the 0.8 that has been considered in the literature [7].

Based on the above results, a lattice structure with balance optimum performance would have the following design variables set at $Y_{RVE} = 8.0$ mm, $\alpha = 0.82$, $\beta = 0.7$ comprised of $R_m = 0.35$ mm and $R_b = 0.50$ mm. In Figure 10, the mesh model of the lattice structure with the aforementioned design is depicted. The resulting properties normalised by the relative density of 0.35 give specific compressive stiffness of $1220 \cdot 10^6$ mm²/s² and out-of-plane shear stiffness of $424.8 \cdot 10^6$ mm²/s².

Figure 8: (a) Specific compressive stiffness as a function of Y_{RVE} , and (b) specific out-of-plane shear stiffness as a function of Y_{RVE} for relative densities $RD = 0.40, 0.35$ and 0.30 and varying the factor α .

Figure 9: (a) Specific compressive stiffness as a function of factor α , and (b) specific out-of-plane shear stiffness as a function of factor α for relative densities $RD = 0.35$ varying the factor α .

Figure 10: Optimised lattice structure with RD = 0.35.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The unit cell of a lattice material was optimised by considering constraints for the design variables which are associated with stereolithography 3D printing. The effect of tapering the unit-cell struts was investigated in terms of compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses through a multi-objective evolutionary optimisation linked with a FE modelling framework. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Tapering the struts has a beneficial effect on both compressive and out-of-plane shear stiffnesses, which can be increased up to 11% and 5%, respectively. The optimum tapering ratio (β) is independent of the Y_{RVE} and relative density. The optimum β is approximately 0.7 with an optimum uniform cross-section length (α) factor at ~ 0.82 .
- The height of the RVE is the main design variable influencing the two objectives. Increased height close to the upper bound of 10 mm results in the highest specific compressive stiffness and ~ 7 mm to the largest specific out-of-plane shear stiffness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council through the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Composites Science, Engineering and Manufacturing (Grant number EP/S021728/1).

REFERENCES

- [1] H. S. Abdulhadi and A. Mian, “Effect of strut length and orientation on elastic mechanical response of modified body-centered cubic lattice structures,” *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part L J. Mater. Des. Appl.*, vol. 233, no. 11, pp. 2219–2233, 2019, doi: 10.1177/1464420719841084.
- [2] M. M. Osman, M. Shazly, E. A. El-Danaf, P. Jamshidi, and M. M. Attallah, “Compressive behavior of stretched and composite microlattice metamaterial for energy absorption applications,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 184, no. December 2019, p. 107715, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107715.
- [3] H. Zhou *et al.*, “Design of self-supporting lattices for additive manufacturing,” *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, vol. 148, no. April 2020, p. 104298, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jmps.2021.104298.
- [4] X. Xiao *et al.*, “Improved Compressive Properties of Lattice Structure Based on an Implicit

- Surface Hybrid Optimization Design Method via Selective Laser Melting,” *Metals (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. 1477, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/met12091477.
- [5] Z. Xiao, Y. Yang, R. Xiao, Y. Bai, C. Song, and D. Wang, “Evaluation of topology-optimized lattice structures manufactured via selective laser melting,” *Mater. Des.*, vol. 143, pp. 27–37, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2018.01.023.
- [6] M. Zhao, D. Z. Zhang, Z. Li, T. Zhang, H. Zhou, and Z. Ren, “Design, mechanical properties, and optimization of BCC lattice structures with taper struts,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 295, no. May, p. 115830, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.115830.
- [7] T. Tancogne-Dejean, A. B. Spierings, and D. Mohr, “Additively-manufactured metallic micro-lattice materials for high specific energy absorption under static and dynamic loading,” *Acta Mater.*, vol. 116, pp. 14–28, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.actamat.2016.05.054.
- [8] Formlabs, “Form 3+.” <https://formlabs.com/eu/3d-printers/form-3/>.
- [9] FormLabs, “Standard Materials for High-Resolution Rapid Prototyping,” pp. 1–3, 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://formlabs-media.formlabs.com/datasheets/Standard-DataSheet.pdf>.
- [10] A. R. Melro and R. Manno, “Microscale representative volume element: generation and statistical characterization,” *Multi-Scale Contin. Mech. Model. Fibre-Reinforced Polym. Compos.*, pp. 31–54, 2021, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-818984-9.00002-0.
- [11] E. J. Barbero, *Finite Element Analysis of Composite Materials Using Abaqus*. 2013.
- [12] K. Ushijima, W. J. Cantwell, R. A. W. Mines, S. Tsopanos, and M. Smith, “An investigation into the compressive properties of stainless steel micro-lattice structures,” *J. Sandw. Struct. Mater.*, vol. 13, pp. 303–329, 2011, doi: 10.1177/1099636210380997.
- [13] E. Ptochos and G. Labeas, “Elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio determination of micro-lattice cellular structures by analytical, numerical and homogenisation methods,” *J. Sandw. Struct. Mater.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 597–626, 2012, doi: 10.1177/1099636212444285.
- [14] M. T. M. I. . Natick, “MATLAB Version: R2021a gamultiobj,” 2021. <https://uk.mathworks.com/help/gads/gamultiobj.html>.
- [15] X. Cao, S. Duan, J. Liang, W. Wen, and D. Fang, “Mechanical properties of an improved 3D-printed rhombic dodecahedron stainless steel lattice structure of variable cross section,” *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 145, no. June, pp. 53–63, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2018.07.006.